

Participation Platforms: Semi-structured Interview Guide for Public Servants

The interview starts by introducing ourselves, the topic of our research and how this topic relates to the interviews. Afterwards, we kindly ask for permission to record the interview. At last, we start asking the following questions and follow-up questions if more details could be relevant for our study.

Q: Which platform have you chosen and what do you use it for?

Q: How did you do this before using such a platform?

Q: What made you choose this platform specifically?

Q: Did you consider choosing another platform?

With this question we would like to know if the public servants are aware of the other available platforms.

We would now like ask more specific questions into what the respondent thinks are the main advantages or disadvantages of the platform he/she uses.

Q: What do you see as the biggest advantages of participation platforms in general and this platform specifically?

Q: Of course, perfection is not possible, could you identify some current negative sides or challenges you experienced?

- Why do you think these challenges occurred?
- What measures were taken to tackle these challenges?

After these questions, we introduce our preliminary framework composed out of early results from the online survey. The most important characteristics are shown, and our methodology is explained in how these were retrieved.

Q: Do you pay attention to the following characteristics? Why and how much?

- The platform is easy to use (*user friendly*)
- The platform is often mentioned in media through marketing (*promotion*)
- The platform is easy and fast to find online (*accessible*)
- Citizens from every age group, education... are active on the platform (*representative*)
- The ideas from the platform are considered and used by the (local) government
- The ideas on the platform are anonymous (*privacy/anonymity*)
- The same ideas are grouped for a comprehensive overview on the platform
- The platform offers a safe connection for the users (no chance of *hacking*)
- The platform offers free access for the users

Q: For you, what are the most important characteristics of a participation platform? (Can be a characteristic from our framework or not)

Q: Is it possible to identify some characteristics you deem important that are not identified in our framework?

Q: What would be an ideal platform?

The basic questions about the identified characteristics are now asked. However, we try to identify some more important characteristics that were difficult to ask to citizens, like database management and closing the gap between the duality of e-participation.

Q: How important is an accurate database structure and how is this managed?

➔ Have any problems occurred before?

Q: Are your users representative of the population? If not, how have you tried to rectify this issue?

Here we try to investigate the most representative age group of the users of their platform and what they do to broaden their audience.

Q: How do you close the link between government-led and citizen-led platforms on social media?

We end our interview if no additional questions come up, and we thank the respondent for his/her attention and time. We keep them up to date after our thesis is finished to tell our conclusions and recommendations in the hope it will be implemented in the next generation of platforms.